

CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR ENGLISH TEACHERS: WHY AND HOW

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Abstract: This work explores the significance of continuing professional development (CPD) for teachers in the context of educational reform and global trends. It highlights how CPD extends beyond initial teacher training and qualification, emphasizing the ongoing need for teachers to deepen subject expertise and enhance skills like critical thinking and problem-solving.

Key words: Continuing Professional Development (CPD), Teacher Training, Educational Reform, Lifelong Learning, Professional Growth, Globalization, Critical Thinking, Teaching Standards

Nowadays, in every country striving for development, special attention is being given to education, and new laws and decisions are being adopted to reform the educational system. Notably, the **United Nations** adopted a new education concept in 2015 for the period up to 2030. Among the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**¹ set out in this concept, **Goal 4 - "Quality Education"** outlines globally important tasks. This goal emphasizes not only ensuring inclusive and equitable education for all but also prioritizes the **professional development of teachers.**

Teacher professional development is regarded as the **foundation of quality education.** For this purpose, countries need to:

- Involve teachers in continuous professional development (CPD) programs,
- Develop modern pedagogical and digital competencies,
- Provide social and economic support for teachers,
- Encourage their engagement in scientific and innovative activities,
- Expand opportunities for international cooperation and experience exchange.

Continuous professional development (CPD) refers to the ongoing process in which a teacher consistently updates their knowledge, skills, and competencies, works on self-improvement, remains open to innovations, and enhances their pedagogical mastery. This is a lifelong process and reflects a teacher's responsibility toward their profession.

Among the researchers studying teachers' continuous professional development, **Cuban**² (1990) emphasizes that **teachers must be at the center**

of reforms, as they are the ones who must implement high standards directly in the classroom.

According to Loucks-Horsley, Hewson, Love, and Stiles³ (1998) in order to implement educational reform requirements, teachers must delve deeply into the subjects they teach—meaning they must have a strong command of their disciplines. They highlight that teachers should not only be capable of delivering fundamental knowledge but also be skilled in developing students' critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

When discussing the differences between professional development and continuing professional development (CPD), scholars provide the following definitions. According to Stevenson⁴ (2010), CPD is defined as: "The professional development of a teacher after the stages of initial training, qualification acquisition, and induction into the profession."

From this definition, it can be concluded that professional development begins during the initial teacher training phase, while continuing professional development (CPD) refers to the advancement that occurs after qualification has been obtained.

However, Friedman and Phillips⁵ (2004) argue that this seemingly simple definition actually masks a complex and controversial concept. They point out that confusion arises due to the variety of perspectives and interpretations regarding the purposes and benefits of CPD. Ushie⁶(2009) describes CPD as an integral part of teaching practice, particularly in the context of expanding educational opportunities and increasing globalization, essential for maintaining and enhancing educational standards.

Coolahan⁷ (2002), meanwhile, defines continuing professional development as lifelong learning. When discussing models and types of continuing professional development (CPD) for teachers, we can note that they are generally organized into two main groups:

1. Activities related to CPD organized in collaboration with an institution or organization
2. Individually conducted activities that contribute to professional development

Institution-Based Continuing Professional Development Models

- Professional development schools
- Collaborations between universities and schools
- Inter-institutional partnerships
- School networks
- Teacher networks
- Distance (online) learning

Individual Continuing Professional Development Models

- Traditional and clinical observations (lesson analysis, open lessons)
- Student performance assessment
- Participation in seminars, courses, workshops, etc.
- Collaborative or peer-based development
- Case-based learning
- Observing best practices
- Reflective models (journaling, monthly reports)
- Maintaining a portfolio
- Action research
- Using teacher narratives (teacher stories)
- Self-study
- Project-based models (e.g., participating in competitions)
- Skills development models
- Teachers' involvement in new roles (as leaders or managers)
- Intergenerational or "cascade" models
- Coaching/mentoring (mentor-apprentice or guiding mentorship)

In conclusion, the ongoing changes in today's education system demand that teachers not only deliver knowledge but also become professionals who **constantly work on themselves**, are **open to innovations**, and **take responsibility** for their role. In particular, for **foreign language teachers**, ensuring **continuing professional development** through a variety of activities enables them to **consistently enhance their professional skills** and take **ownership of their responsibilities**. Teachers can engage in continuing professional development through the following activities:

- **Participating in both offline and online training courses** aimed at improving their professional skills;
- **Presenting practical research articles and theses** addressing challenges in teaching students, sharing ideas, and seeking solutions at scientific-practical conferences;

Regularly analyzing their own teaching practices, conducting reflection through electronic or traditional portfolios, which enables them to continuously assess and enrich their professional activities with new approaches and innovations.

References:

1. UN General Assembly (UNGA). 2015 Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development;
2. Cuban, L. (1990). How Teachers Taught (3rd ed.). New York: Longman;
3. Loucks-Horsley, Hewson, Love, & Stiles, 1998; National Commission on Teaching and America's Future, 1996;
4. Stevenson, A., ed., 2010. Oxford dictionary of English [online]. Oxford: Oxford University Press;
5. Тошбоева Б. О. (2022). Теоретический анализ понимания процесса изучения иностранных языков. Herald pedagogiki Nauka i Praktyka, 2. <https://zenodo.org/record/6451688>
6. Тошбоева Б. О. (2019). Чет тилларини ўқитишда ахборот коммуникация технологияларининг ўрни. In Педагогика фанининг долзарб муаммолари р. 204 страница.
7. Тошбоева Б. О. (2024). Создание условий для единства мышления и речи: психолого-методические основы обучения иностранным языкам. Зарубежная лингвистика и лингводидактика.

